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SCANNING RELEVANCY BETWEEN FACE BOOK AND STUDENTS` ACADEMIC ENGAGEMENT

B K Suthar

Ph D Scholar, Pacific University, Udaipur (Rajasthan), India

R Lathangi

Ph D Scholar, Pacific University, Udaipur (Rajasthan), India

Dr. Shamal Pradhan

Asst. Prof. MSU of Baroda (Gujarat), India

Abstract

Purpose: The face book usage rate is high amongst the college students and face book intends to be an engaging platform going so far as to determine their success in terms of their academic engagement. This paper aims to examine the relationship between face book usage and academic engagement in context to students of Faculty of Commerce, M S University of Baroda

Design/methodology/approach: This is correlation type of study and consists of primary and secondary data. The survey questionnaires were distributed to the students of final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda. (264 out of 470) by employing sample size determinants like; confidence level, confidence interval and population. The non-probability convenience sampling process is employed for primary data collection. The questionnaire consists of factors namely; socio psychological factor, trust and privacy, socioeconomic status and academic engagement with 40 items. All the 264 respondents are considered as valid respondents for further investigations. The collected data are analyzed by conducting scale reliability test, descriptive statistics, factor analysis and regression analysis with a view to assess the correlations between face book usage and academic engagement of the respondents. IBM SPSS 20.0 is used for data analysis as a statistical tool.

Findings: The collected data explores on significant and positive relationship between demographic profile and socio psychological factor, socioeconomic status, including academic engagement of respondents. The results of data analysis is also shows that Face book is more likely to operate as a distracting influence for the respondents.

Research Implications/Limitations: The study of this paper indicates on both the positive and negative relationship between face book usage and academic engagement of students. The face book usage by respondents may develop their

social networking and can be proved such a social media as powerful tool for students` academic career development by employing appropriate face book usage dimensions. Further research can be held with more samples by extending the area of research.

Introduction

Face book is preeminent social networking site and can connect friends, family, and business associates. This powerful tool of social media can play vital role on strengthening students` academic career in higher education. "More faces, less books "can be converted into "less faces, more books" through their academic engagement. This study examines the relevancy between Face Book (FB) usage and academic engagement in context to students of final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda the relationship between face book usage and academic engagement in context to students of Faculty of Commerce, M S University of Baroda This is correlation type of study and consists of primary and secondary data. The survey questionnaire was administered through email and in person (264 out of 470) by employing sample size determinants like; confidence level, confidence interval and population. The non-probability convenience sampling process is employed for primary data collection. The questionnaire consists of factors namely; socio psychological, trust and privacy, socioeconomic status and academic engagement with 40 items. The collected data are analyzed by conducting scale reliability test, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and regression analysis. IBM SPSS is employed for data analysis as a statistical tool. The data analysis results reveal on acceptable positive correlations between student academic engagement and factors like; trust and privacy,

Research Gaps and Research Objectives

The following important research gaps are identified on the basis of literature reviewed for this study.

- (1) There is no substantial literature on relevancy between face book usage and student academic engagement of under graduate students in Indian context.
- (2) Socio-psychological status, trust-cum-privacy and socio-economic factor are not examined in relation with student academic engagement who are using face book in Indian context by the researchers in past.

Thus, this proposed research is intended to fill the research gap and to examine how student academic engagement is related with students` socio-psychological status, trust-cum-privacy and socio-economic on using face book. The study also reflects on need to strengthen students` academic engagement through face book usage instead of strengthening only social network.

The proposed research work has research objectives namely (1) To study the relationship between face book usage and student academic engagement in context to the students of final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda (2) To determine the factor that has strongest positive significance relationship observed with student academic engagement in context to the students of final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda(3) To determine the most influential factor to student academic engagement during this study.

Research Questions

- (1) Is there positive significance relationship between student academic engagement and socio psychological factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda?
- (2) Is there positive significance relationship between student academic engagement and trust and privacy in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda?

(3) Is there positive significance relationship between student academic engagement and socioeconomic in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda?

Research Implications/Limitations: The study of this paper indicates on both the positive and negative relationship between face book usage and academic engagement of students. The face book usage by respondents may develop their social networking and can be proved such a social media as powerful tool for students` academic career development by employing appropriate face book usage dimensions. Further research can be held with more samples by extending the area of research.

Review of Literature

Social Media - terms used to describe the new generation of digital, computerized, or networked information and communication technologies. These can take many different forms, including internet forums, blogs, wikis, and podcasts, and picture-, music- and video-sharing. Examples of social media applications are Google Groups, Wikipedia, MySpace, and Face book, you Tube, Second Liie, Flickr and Twitter There is a fair amount of professional and popular interest in the effects of social media on college student development and success (Abramson, 2011; Kamenetz, 2011) The most popular social media website for college students is Face book, and research shows that anywhere between 85 and 99% of college students use Face book (Hargittai, 2008a; Jones & Fox, 2009; Matney & Borland, 2009). it is important to acknowledge that there are persistent differences along gender, racial, and socioeconomic lines in technology adoption and use, often referred to as the digital divide (Cooper & Weaver, 2003; DiMaggio, Hargittai, Celeste, & Shafer, 2004; Hargittai, 2008b; Junco, Merson, & Salter, 2010; Kaiser Family Foundation, 2004). Accordingly, studies on Internet addiction have proliferated (*Byun et al. 2009; Chou, Condron, & Belland, 2005*). *Surprisingly, relatively few of the studies have focused on college students, even though college students have been found to have both high levels of Internet use (Kandell, 1998;)* as well as depression (; Peterson, 2002;). The studies on college students differ in terms of whether they measure Internet addiction or simply Internet use, and the specific social and psychological variables they investigate. The results are mixed – some studies find negative relationships (e.g., Morahan-Martin & Schumaker, 2000; Morahan-Martin & Schumaker, 2003), some positive relationships (e.g., Morgan & Cotton, 2003), and others no relationships (e.g., Anderson, 2001). Relatively recent studies focusing on Internet addiction among college students have tended to find primarily negative correlates. Morahan-Martin and Schumaker (2000) investigated the relationship between pathological Internet use (PIU) and loneliness among 277 undergraduate students. They found that loneliness was associated with pathological use. In a later reanalysis of the same data (Morahan-Martin & Schumaker, 2003), they found that lonely users were more likely than the non-lonely to seek emotional support online, find more satisfaction with online versus offline friends, and to be experiencing more disturbances in their daily lives. Also using the PUI scale, Niemz, Griffins and Banyard (2005) studied 371 British college students and found that pathological users reported more perceived academic, social and interpersonal problems as well as lower self-esteem. However, there was not a difference between pathological and non-pathological users on the General Heath Questionnaire, a measure of anxiety, depression and self-confidence. Chak and Leung's (2004) study included 722 Internet users between the ages of 12 and 26, some of which were college students. They found that Internet addiction was associated with shyness, external locus of control, and a belief in the effect of chance on outcomes. Fortson, Scotti, Chen, Malone and Del Ben (2007) found that abuse of and dependence on the on the Internet was associated with depression and lower levels of face-to-face interaction among 411 undergraduates. However, depression was not related to amount of time online. Several studies have examined the association between time on the Internet and social and psychological factors, and these studies seem less likely to find negative associations. Morgan and Cotton's (2003) study of college freshmen found that increased time spent shopping, playing games and doing research was associated with higher levels of depression, but sending e-mail and visiting chat rooms was associated with lower levels. Using path analysis, LaRose, Eastin and Gregg (2001) found that higher Internet use was only indirectly associated with depression and the relationship was mediated by Internet self-efficacy and anticipated Internet stress among 171 college

students. They also found that higher use of e-mail to communicate with known others was related to fewer symptoms of depression. Anderson (2001) studied the relationships between Internet use and perceived effects on academics, extracurricular activities, sleep patterns and real-life relationships among a large sample (1,300) of college students. Only sleep patterns were associated with Internet use. Finally, Gordon, Juang and Syed (2007) studied depression, social anxiety, and family cohesion and Internet use for particular purposes among 312 college students. Only Internet use for coping purposes was associated with depression, social anxiety and family cohesion. A limitation of almost all of these studies is that the extent to which the samples represent particular student populations is unknown. Some samples were generated by administration of questionnaires to college classes (Anderson, 2001; Chou & Hsiao, 2000; Gordon et al., 2007; LaRose et al., 2001; Morahan-Martin & Schumacher, 2000, 2003), yet none of the studies reported an estimated response rate or an analysis of the extent to which the sample was representative of the student population. Other studies have used self-selected samples (Ko et al., 2008), subject pools (Fortson et al., 2007) or Internet snowballing (Chak & Leung, 2004; Niemi et al., 2005). Samples that are self-selected or employ snowballing may be especially at risk of over-representing heavy Internet users. Byun et al. (2009) also note similar sampling problems with Internet addiction studies

Face book privacy settings are not always fully utilized. Users can change the way others see their private information, Lange, R. L. & Lampe, C. (2008) hypothesized that privacy settings may not be adjusted due to ignorance or the “it won’t happen to me” assumption. Lange’s study also points out that when users click the “Accept Terms and Conditions” button when joining a site or adding an Application, they tend not to read the fine print, which may say that the user is (unknowingly) agreeing to sell or give away his/her personal information. Sherman (2008) adds that a term such as “Privacy Policy” on a website may make users automatically assume that their information is safe when that may not actually be the case notable exception is Gross & Acquisti (2005), who looked at “actual field data about the usage and the inferred privacy preferences of more than 4,000 [Facebook] users” at Carnegie Mellon University (CMU).

Astin (1984) defined engagement as “the amount of physical and psychological energy that the student devotes to the academic experience” Today, engagement is conceptualized as the time and effort students invest in educational activities that are empirically linked to desired college outcomes (Kuh, 2009). Engagement encompasses various factors, including investment in the academic experience of college, interactions with faculty, involvement in co-curricular activities, and interaction with peers (Kuh, 2009; Pascarella & Terenzini, 2005). Kuh (2009) emphasizes two major aspects: in-class (or academic) engagement and out-of-class engagement in educationally relevant (or cocurricular) activities, both of which are important to student success.

Pascarella and Terenzini (2005) highlight the relationship between student engagement, student development, and success: The Heiberger and Harper (2008) study focused solely on Facebook use, while the HERI (2007) study focused on all social networking websites. Both the Heiberger and Harper (2008) and HERI (2007) studies found positive correlations between social networking website use and college

Research Methodology

This type of study is correlation and aims to analyze and examine the relevance of face book usage and academic engagement in context to students of final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda The questionnaire consists of factors namely; socio psychological, trust and privacy, socioeconomic status, and academic engagement with 40 items.5-point Likert scale technique(Likert,1931) is used for questionnaire scaling. All the 264 respondents are considered as valid respondents for further investigations. The collected data are analyzed by conducting scale reliability test, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and regression analysis including other applicable tests with a view to analyze the correlations between face book usage and academic engagement of the respondents. IBM SPSS is employed for data analysis as a statistical tool. The following statistical formula has supported on finalization of sampling size

$$ss = \frac{Z^2 * (p) * (1-p)}{}$$

$$c^2$$

Where: Z = Z value (e.g. 1.96 for 95% confidence level)
 p = percentage picking a choice, expressed as decimal
 (.5 used for sample size needed) c = confidence interval, expressed as decimal
 (e.g., .04 = ±4)

The structured disguised questionnaire was administered to respondents through email and in person by consisting factors such as; demographic profile of respondents,. Both types of primary and secondary data are taken into consideration for investigation. The adopted scaling technique in questionnaire is 5 point Likert scale (strongly disagree to strongly agree,) because non-parametric statistics is used (Jamieson, 2004).The collected data are analyzed for demographic profile, scale reliability test, descriptive statistics, factor analysis and regression analysis. ..

The following hypotheses are formed to meet the objectives of the study.

H01 No significant association between student academic engagements and socio psychological factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

H02: No significant association between student academic engagements and trust cum privacy factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

H03: No significant association between student academic engagements and socioeconomic factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

The following research model is framed for hypothesis testing and further investigation.

Results and Discussion

The following results are obtained after analyzing the collected data from the respondents. The results are in tabulated form in annexure.

Table-1 indicates the descriptive analysis for demographic information indicated that among the analyzed samples (n=264) consisting of final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda. In terms of age group, 108 respondents are under the age group of 19-20(40.9%) and 156(59.1%) respondents are under the age group of 20-21 years. In terms of study semester, 112(42.4%) respondents are pursuing fifth semester of under graduation and 152(57.6%) respondents are pursuing sixth and final semester of their graduation. In terms of financial status of respondents, 212(80.3%) respondents are financially dependent and 52(19.7%) respondents are financially independent. The face book activities in a week consume their time within three slots. 116(43.9%) respondents consume their time at the range of less than five hours in week. 82 (31.1%) respondents consume their time at the range of 6-10 hours in a week. 94(35.6%) respondents consume their time towards face book activities at the range of more than ten hours in a week. The frequency of using face book of the respondents is also grouped in three groups. 94(35.6%) respondents have frequency of using face book is ten or more than ten times in a week. 102 (38.6%) respondents have frequency of using face book is 11-20 times in a week. 68 (25.8%) respondents have frequency of using face book is 21-30 times in a week. In terms of the most favorite activity on face book is asked to the respondents with 14 different activities as shown in table-1 of annexure. "Tagging photos" activity is responded as the highest by the respondents during the study. (35 respondents i.e. 13.3%) The lowest response is registered for "playing games" (6 respondents i.e. 2.3%)

Table-2 of annexure indicates the results on scale reliability test of factors considered for this study, namely, socio psychological factor, trust and privacy, socioeconomic status and academic engagement with 40 items. Reliability and validity of the scale is important for obtaining meaningful results. Validity and reliability are the tools used to evaluate the characteristics of a good measurement and these tools involved a measurement of accuracy and applicability (Malhotra, 2004; Cooper and Schindler, 2001). The main concern for performing validity and reliability is to develop a measurement that reflects a true score of the variables being measured (Churchill and Iacobucci, 2002). The Cronbach alpha coefficient ranges from 0 to 1 with a minimum of 0.6 while other studies suggest that anything above 0.7 suggest high levels of internal reliability (Hair *et al.*, 1998). Nunnally (1978) suggested that an alpha value of 0.7 is acceptable. Many studies have used reliability to test their modified service quality scale that ranged from 0.6 to 0.96 (Chowdhary & Prakash, 2007; Caro & Garcia, 2007; Akbaba, 2006; Jabnoun & Khalifa, 2005; Sureshchandar, Rajendran & Anantharaman, 2002; Dabholkar, Thorpe & Rentz, 1996;). George and Mallery (2003) provide the following rules of thumb: " $\alpha > .9$ – Excellent, $\alpha > .8$ – Good, $\alpha > .7$ – Acceptable, $\alpha > .6$ – Questionable, $\alpha > .5$ – Poor, and $\alpha < .5$ – Unacceptable" (p. 231) For the purpose of this research the researcher had used Cronbach alpha coefficient (Cronbach, 1951), the most common method for testing reliability, and 0.6 will be used as the minimal accepted level. Cronbach alpha for "Socio-psychological Status" is registered as 0.732. For "Trust cum Privacy" factor, Cronbach alpha is registered as 0.759. Cronbach alpha for "Socio-economic status Status" is registered as 0.730 and Cronbach alpha is registered as 0.721. These results for four factors validates to move for the further investigation.

Table-4 indicates the results on descriptive statistics of collected data from the respondents. The table consists of sample size (n), number of items, range, minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation and variance. The value of mean for "Socio Psychological Factor" (SPF) is 2.48 and standard deviation is 1.44. The value of mean for "Trust cum Privacy" (TP) is 2.54 and standard deviation is 1.55. The value of mean for "Socio-economic Status" (SS) is 2.56 and standard deviation is 1.51. The value of mean for "Academic Engagement" (AE) is 2.84 and standard deviation is 1.64. The range is 4, minimum is 1, maximum is 5 and highest value of variance is 2.70 for student academic engagement. These results lead to move for the further investigation on examining relevancy between student academic engagement and other factors, namely, socio psychological factor, trust and privacy, socioeconomic status and academic engagement with 40 items

Table-5 indicates on the results on data reduction process. Factor analysis is conducted for this study with a view to data reduction. There are two categories of general recommendations in terms of minimum sample size in factor analysis. One category says that the absolute number of cases (N) is important, while another says that the subject-to-variable ratio (p) is important. Arrindell and van der Ende (1985), Velicer and Fava (1998), and McCollum, Widaman, Zhang and Hong (1999) have reviewed many of these recommendations. Rule of 250: Cattell (1978) claimed the minimum desirable N to be 250 (in MacCallum, Widaman, Zhang & Hong, 1999, p84).is employed in this case.

Table-5A-5D indicates the results on KMO values. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (Kaiser, 1974) is the measure of sampling adequacy, which varies between 0 and 1. The values closer to 1 are better and the value of 0.6 is the suggested minimum. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is the test for null hypothesis that the correlation matrix has an identity matrix. Taking this into consideration, these tests provide the minimum standard to proceed for Factor Analysis.

Table-5A indicates the results on KMO and Bartlett's Test for "socio-psychological factor" of this study. For this data, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy value is registered at 0.723, which falls into the range of being good. So that factor analysis is appropriate for these data. Bartlett's test shows that there is some relationship between variables. The value is highly significant ($p < 0.05$), and therefore factor analysis is appropriate.

Table-5B indicates the results on KMO and Bartlett's Test for "trust cum privacy" of this study. For this data, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy value is registered at 0.733, which falls into the range of being good. So that factor analysis is appropriate for these data. Bartlett's test shows that there is some relationship between variables. The value is highly significant ($p < 0.05$), and therefore factor analysis is appropriate.

Table-5C indicates the results on KMO and Bartlett's Test for "socio-economic status" of this study. For this data, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy value is registered at 0.704, which falls into the range of being good. So that factor analysis is appropriate for these data. Bartlett's test shows that there is some relationship between variables. The value is highly significant ($p < 0.05$), and therefore factor analysis is appropriate.

Table-5D indicates the results on KMO and Bartlett's Test for "student academic engagement" of this study. For this data, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy value is registered at 0.741, which falls into the range of being good. So that factor analysis is appropriate for these data. Bartlett's test shows that there is some relationship between variables. The value is highly significant ($p < 0.05$), and therefore factor analysis is appropriate. The results of table-5A-5D concludes that correlations can be investigated amongst the variables by conducting linear regression analysis.

Table-5E-5H indicates the results on communalities. It indicates the amount of variance in each variable that is accounted for. Initial communalities are estimates of the variance in each variable accounted for by all components or factors. Extraction communalities are estimates of the variance in each variable accounted for by the factors (or components) in the factor solution. Small values (< 0.5) are not fit well with the factor solution, and dropped from the analysis. Minimum and maximum extraction values are mentioned in tables 5E-5H(0.419-0.862)

Table-5I indicates the results on scree plot for 40 items consisted in the questionnaire. The scree plot graphs the eigenvalue against the factor number. From the eleventh factor, the line is almost flat, meaning the each successive factor is accounting for smaller and smaller amounts of the total variance

Table-5J-5M indicates the results on total variance explained. Terms of table5J-5Mcan be explained in the following manner.

Factor: The initial number of factors is the same as the number of variables used in the factor analysis.

Initial Eigen values: Eigen values are the variances of the factors.

Total: This column contains the eigenvalues. The first factor will always account for the most variance (and hence have the highest eigenvalue), and the next factor will account for as much of the left over variance as it can, and so on. Hence, each successive factor will account for less and less variance.

% of Variance: This column contains the percent of total variance accounted for by each factor.

Cumulative %: This column contains the cumulative percentage of variance accounted for by the current and all preceding factors.

Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings: The number of rows in this panel of the table correspond to the number of factors retained. In this study, three factors be retained, so there are three rows, one for each retained factor. The values in this panel of the table are calculated in the same way as the values in the left panel, except that here the values are based on the common variance. The values in this panel of the table will always be lower than the values in the left panel of the table, because they are based on the common variance, which is always smaller than the total variance.

Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings: The values in this panel of the table represent the distribution of the variance after the varimax rotation. Varimax rotation tries to maximize the variance of each of the factors, so the total amount of variance accounted for is redistributed over the three extracted factors..

Table-5N-5Q indicates the results on rotated component matrix. These tables contain the rotated factor loadings (factor pattern matrix), which represent both how the variables are weighted for each factor but also the correlation between the variables and the factor. Because these are correlations, possible values range from -1 to +1. The idea of rotation is to reduce the number factors on which the variables under investigation have high loadings. Rotation does not actually change anything but makes the interpretation of the analysis easier. The results shown in table5J-5M lead to move for the further analysis with the variables.

Table-6 indicates the results on regression analysis with a view to determine association amongst the factors considered for the study. In this study, "student academic engagement"(AE) is considered as dependent variable and the rest of the three factors are considered as independent variable,namely,"socio-psychological factor"(SP),"trust cum privacy"(TP) and ""socio-economic status"(SS) Each factor has 10 items. Linear Regression analysis is conducted for testing the hypothesis formed on the basis of objectives.All the three hypothesizes are tested and summarized in the following manner.

H01 No significant association between student academic engagements and socio psychological factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

H01 There is significant association between student academic engagements and socio psychological factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

The model summary part of table-6 indicates the results on R, R², adjusted R² and standard error of estimate. It gives essential information revealing how well our regression model fit (or did not fit) the observed data. In this study, R=0.844, R²=0.712 and adjusted R² =0.708. Adjusted R square calculates the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable accounted by the explanatory variables. Here, adjusted R square is registered as 0.708 for DV: AE1 (i.e. dependent variableAE1:" I spend most of the time on FB" and IDV: SP1-10 (i.e. independent variables of socio-psychological factor) It means there is 70.8% association between AE1*SP. The ANOVA portion of table-6 shows that for the overall range of regression, $F = 18.457$ with 5 degrees of freedom, with a probability (in the Sig column) well below 0.05.i.e.sig.0.000, where $p < 0.05$ so the regression is significant. ForAE1*SP1-10, it is interpreted that 81.2% of the variation exists between AE1 and SP1-10. The higher value of beta, standard beta and t value indicates closed positive relationship between AE1*SP2.($\beta=0.912$,standard $\beta=0.900$, $t=27.520$) The ANOVA portion of table-6 shows that for the overall range of regression, $F = 180.457$ with 5 degrees of freedom, with a probability (in the Sig column) well below 0.05.i.e.sig.0.000, where $p < 0.05$ so the regression is significant. For AE1*SP7, adjusted R² = 0.926.t is interpreted that 92.6% of the variation exists between AE1 and SP1-10. The higher value of beta, standard beta and t value indicates closed positive relationship between AE1*SP7 .It means, significant positive association is observed for (AE1:" I spend most of the time on FB"*SP2:" It affects the social interaction amongst the students" and AE1: "I

spend most of the time on FB” * SP2” * SP7.” It gives social identity”). The other variables registered as poor association in terms of R², adjusted R², beta value, t value, F value and significant value. So that, such variables are dropped from the discussion. It means there is significant positive relationship between socio-psychological factor and student academic engagement. So that, H01 is rejected and H11 is accepted.

H02: No significant association between student academic engagements and trust cum privacy factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

H02: There is significant association between student academic engagements and trust cum privacy factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

Here in table-6, adjusted R square is registered as 0.911 for DV: AE3 (i.e. dependent variable AE3:” FB helps me in learning new concepts” and IDV: TP1-10 (i.e. independent variables of trust cum privacy factor) It means there is 91.1% association between AE3*TP. The ANOVA portion of table-6 shows that for the overall range of regression, $F = 948.362$ with 5 degrees of freedom, with a probability (in the Sig column) well below 0.05 i.e. sig.0.000, where $p < 0.05$ so the regression is significant. For AE3*TP1-10, it is interpreted that 81.2% of the variation exists between AE1 and SP1-10. The higher value of beta, standard beta and t value indicates closed positive relationship between AE3*TP8. ($\beta = 0.927$, standard $\beta = 0.982$, $t = 51.913$) For AE3*TP8, adjusted R² = 0.796. t is 61.934. It is interpreted that 79.6% of the variation exists between AE3 and TP1-10. The higher value of beta, standard beta and t value indicates closed positive relationship between AE3*TP9. It means, significant positive association is observed for (AE3:”FB helps me in learning new concepts:” * TP8:” FB is technically reliable.”). It means there is significant positive relationship between trust cum security factor and student academic engagement. So that, H02 is rejected and H12 is accepted.

H03: No significant association between student academic engagements and socioeconomic factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

H13: There is significant association between student academic engagements and socioeconomic factor in context to final year commerce graduation in specialization with management, faculty of commerce M S University of Baroda

Here in table-6, adjusted R square is registered as 0.838 for DV: AE1 (i.e. dependent variable AE3:” I spend most of the time on FB” and IDV: SS1-10 (i.e. independent variables of socio-economic factor) It means there is 83.8% association between AE1*SS1-10. The ANOVA portion of table-6 shows that for the overall range of regression, $F = 323.025$ with 5 degrees of freedom, with a probability (in the Sig column) well below 0.05 i.e. sig.0.000, where $p < 0.05$ so the regression is significant. For AE2*SS1-10, it is interpreted that 83.8% of the variation exists between AE1 and SP1-10. The higher value of beta, standard beta and t value indicates closed positive relationship between AE2*ss3. ($\beta = 0.932$, standard $\beta = 0.958$, $t = 34.456$) For AE3*SS4, adjusted R² = 0.832. t is interpreted that 83.2% of the variation exists between AE2 and SS1-10. The higher value of beta, standard beta and t value indicates closed positive relationship between AE2*SS4. It means, significant positive association is observed for AE1*SS3 and AE2*SS4. (i.e. “I spend most of the time on FB” * “It is a necessity for socioeconomically sound students to be on FB”. FB is a motivational factor to complete the academic endeavors” * “The Status of the person is derived out of his friends list on FB”:) It means there is significant positive relationship between trust cum security factor and student academic engagement. So that, H03 is rejected and H13 is accepted. Thus, the entire three hypotheses are tested and null hypotheses are rejected. As a result, alternative hypotheses are accepted.

Conclusion

The three objectives are satisfied by considering the above discussion. It can be concluded from the above discussion that student academic engagement is significantly correlated with socio-psychological factor, trust cum privacy factor and socio-economic status. AE11*SP2 (i.e. "I spend most of the time on FB" and "It affects the social interaction amongst the students") AE1*SP7 (i.e. "I spend most of the time on FB" and "It gives social identity") AE3*TP5 (i.e. "FB helps me in learning new concepts" and "I trust the information shared by others on the FB") AE3*TP8 (i.e. "FB helps me in learning new concepts" and "FB is technically reliable") AE3*TP99 (i.e. "FB helps me in learning new concepts" and "Interpersonal trust level is high in FB") AE1*SS2 ("I spend most of the time on FB" and "It is a necessity for socioeconomically sound students to be on FB") AE1*SS4 (i.e. "I spend most of the time on FB" and "The Status of the person is derived out of his friends list on FB.") Thus, student academic engagement is correlated with trust cum privacy, socio-psychological factor and socio-economic status All the hypothesis, research questions and objectives are satisfied with the positive outcomes through this investigation.

Third fourth objective of this study is significant positive and highest correlations is registered between two pairs of variables (AE1*SP7 and AE3*TP8). Both the pairs have the value of adjusted R square is 0.926. i.e. correlation is 92.6%. More ever, It can be concluded that students spend most of the time towards FB activities because they believe that FB provides social identity in a better way. It is to be concluded that the students spend their most of the time towards FB activities because it is technically more reliable.

Limitations and scope for further research

This study has certain limitations like; time constraints, area of research, sample size determination and items considered for questionnaire to collect primary data. In this study, questionnaire for primary data collection. is considered for four factors with 40 total items. But, some of the items have received poor results on adjusted R square (<0.0.6), Further research can be held by expanding area of research and with some more items for questionnaire. The sample size also can be increased.

Recommendations

(1) The administrators of MSU of Baroda can conduct awareness programs on using social media for the students. (2) The MSU of Baroda management can pay more concentration on using FB by incorporating the same as extracurricular activities. (3).FB should be proved as a tool for student academic engagement in higher educational institutions. (4) In this study, it appears that Face book is more likely to operate as a distracting influence for the students of MSU of Baroda So that, efforts should be made by MSU of Baroda management to polarize the students on their academic engagement in a better way usage (5) FB can be use for academic career enhancement (6) FB can be proved as a tool for motivational factor to complete the academic endeavors.

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Annexure

Demographic Profile

Table-1

r.No	Demographic	Category	Frequency	Percentage%
1	Gender	Male	128	48.5
		Female	136	51.5
2	Age	19-20 years	108	40.9
		20—21 years	156	59.1
3	Study Semester	Fifth	112	42.4
		Sixth	152	57.6
4	Financial Status	Dependent	212	80.3
		Independent	52	19.7
5	FBC activities in a week:	< 5 hours	116	43.9
		6-10 hours	82	31.1
		> 10 hours	25	25.0
6	FBC Frequency in a week	≤ 10 times	94	35.6
		11-20 times	102	38.6
		2 1-30 times	68	25.8

7	The most Favorite FB activity	First choice		
		Playing games	6	2.3
		Posting status updates	18	6.8
		Sharing links.	12	4.5
		Sending private messages.	20	7.6
		Commenting	15	5.7
		Chatting	28	10.6
		Checking to see what someone is up to	30	11.4
		Posting photos		
		Tagging photos	35	13.3
		Viewing photos	25	9.5
		Posting videos	20	7.6
		Tagging videos.	10	3.8
		Viewing videos.	10	3.8
		Career making	10	3.8
academic	20	7.6		
Other	5	1.9		

Scale Reliability Test- Table-2

Sr.no	Factor	Items	Excluded Items	Valid Items	Measured Cronbach Alpha	Standard Internal Consistency	Decision
1	Socio Psychological Factor	10	0	10	0.732	$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	acceptable
2	Trust and Privacy	10	0	10	0.759	$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	acceptable
3	Socioeconomic Status	10	0	10	0.730	$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	acceptable
4	Academic Engagement	10	0	10	0.721	$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	acceptable

Descriptive Statistics

Table-3

Sr.No.	Factor	n	Items	Range	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD	Variance
1	Socio Psychological Factor	264	10	4	1	5	2.48	1.44	2.07
2	Trust and Privacy	264	10	4	1	5	2.54	1.55	2.41
3	Socioeconomic Status	264	10	4	1	5	2.56	1.51	2.30
4	Academic Engagement	264	10	4	1	5	2.84	1.64	2.70

Factor Analysis- Table-5A

KMO and Bartlett's Test(socio-psychological factor)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.723
Approx. Chi-Square		494.093
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	45
	Sig.	.000

Table5B

KMO and Bartlett's Test(Trust cum Privacy factor)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.733
Approx. Chi-Square		718.988
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	45
	Sig.	.000

Table-5C

KMO and Bartlett's Test(socio-economic status)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.704
Approx. Chi-Square		730.210
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	45
	Sig.	.000

Table-5D

KMO and Bartlett's Test(student academic engagement)

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.741
Approx. Chi-Square		1091.668
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	45
	Sig.	.000

Table-5E

Communalities (socio-psychological factor)

Item	Initial	Extraction
Level of social influence increases on using FB(SP9)	1	0.428
Informational social influence disturb me (SP10)	1	0.813

Table-5F

Communalities (trust cum privacy)

Item	Initial	Extraction
FB will not use my personal information for other purpose(TP6)	1	0.474
FB will not use my personal information for other purpose(TP6)	1	0.824

Table-5G

Communalities (socio-economic status)

Item	Initial	Extraction
Socioeconomic status increase social capital through FB(ss9)	1	0.419

FB users generally have economically sound background(SS10)	1	0.862
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Table-5H
Communalities (student academic engagement)

Item	Initial	Extraction
Student socialization is possible through FB(AE4)	1	0.587
Notifications for lecture note availability, and assessment items(AE8)	1	0.795

Table5I
(SP1-10,TP1-10,SS1-10 and AE1-10)

Table-5J
Total Variance Explained(socio psychological factor)

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.103	31.030	31.030
2	1.313	13.129	44.160
3	1.032	10.323	54.482

.Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table-5K
Total Variance Explained(trust cumprivacy)

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.218	32.175	32.175
2	1.867	18.670	50.845
3	1.087	10.874	61.719

.Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table-5L

Total Variance Explained(socio-economic status)

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.082	30.818	30.818
2	1.957	19.569	50.387
3	1.071	10.709	61.096

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table-5M

Total Variance Explained(student academic engagement)

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.490	34.900	34.900
2	2.369	23.687	58.586
3	1.193	11.927	70.513

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table-5N

Socio-psychological factor
Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component		
	1	2	3
FB usage affects the mindset of students(SPS1)		.776	
FB is not used the way it was originally intended(SPS3)	.672		
It helps to overcome insecurities(SP4)		.718	
FB increases the self esteem of the students(SPS5)	.753		
It distracts the students(SPS6)	.633		
It gives social identity(SPS7)	.649		
Informational social influence disturb me (SPS10)			0.897

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

Table-5O

Trust cum privacy factor
Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component		
	1	2	3
It is safe to display information on FB(TP1)			0.883
Most of the profile sare exaggerated to make the person look more appealing(TP7)	.633		
I display my relationship status on the FB(TP3)		.718	
I trust the information shared by others on the FB(TP6)		.783	
Most of the profile sare exaggerated to make the person look more appealing(TP7)	.633		
FB is technically reliable(TP8)	.699		
Interpersonal trust level is high in FB(TP9)	.798		0.897
Locus of control level is satisfactory in FB(TP10)	.712		

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

Socio-economic status (Table5P)

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component		
	1	2	3
FB users generally have economically sound background(SS1)			0.926
FB users generally have good social reputation(SS2)	.	.802	
Students feel out of place if they are on FB(SS5)		.783	
FB is for education achievement(SS6)	.	.663	
FB is for occupational prestige(SS7)	.816		.
FB is for economic resources(SS8)	.757	.	
Socioeconomic status increase social capital through FB(SS9)	.622		
socioeconomic status relates to larger and denser networks			.610

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

Student Academic Engagement(Table-5Q)

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component		
	1	2	3
I spend most of the time on FB(AE2)	.834		
FB helps me in learning new concepts(AE3)	.802		
Student socialization is possible through FB(AE4)	.676		
A wide variety of technological environment can be exposed through FB(AE5)	.735	.	
FB allows its users to engage in targeted performance(AE6)	.806		.
Increasing interaction with course convenor and fellow students(AE7)		.781	
Participation in general discussion about course topic(AE8)	.622		.859
Exposure to relevant media and learning materials(AE10)			.773

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

Regression Analysis(Table-6)

Regression Analysis(Table-6)															
Model Summary					ANOVA						coefficients				
Factor *	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error Of estimate		Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	sig	Unstd coefficient	Std Beta	t	sig	
DV: AE1 IDV:S P1-10	0.844	0.712	0.708	0.8791	Regression	697.256	5	139.451	180.457	0.000	Beta	Std error	Beta		
					Residual	282.060	365	0.773	SP2:0.912	SP 0.033	SP 0.900	SP2 27.520	0.000		
					Total	979.315	370								
DV:AE1 IDV:S P1-10	0.963	0.927	0.926	0.4395	Regression	891.463	4	222.866	1153.483	0.000	SP7 0.936	SP 0.016	SP 0.996	SP7 61.923	0.000
					Residual	70.715	366	0.193							
					Total	962.178	370								

DV:AE3 IDV:TP1-10	0.955	0.912	0.911	0.4395	Regression	732.935	4	183.234	948.362	0.000	TP5 0.932	TP5 0.019	TP5 0.972	TP5 51.913	0.000
					Residual	70.715	366	0.193							
					Total	803.450	370								
DV:AE3 IDV:TP1-10	0.963	0.927	0.926	0.4430	Regression	907.485	4	226.871	1156.978	0.000	TP8 0.927	TP8 0.016	TP8 0.982	TP8 61.934	0.000
					Residual	71.831	366	0.196							
					Total	979.315	370								
DV:AE7 IDV:TP1-10	0.896	0.803	0.796	0.7222	Regression	722.322	6	128.720	246.788	0.000	TP9 0.886	TP9 0.027	TP9 0.898	TP9 32.560	0.000
					Residual	189.856	364	0.522							
					Total	962.178	370								
DV::AE1 IDV::SS1-10	0.918	0.842	0.838	0.5908	Regression	676.582	6	112.764	323.025	0.000	SS3 0.928	SS 3.027	SS 3.058	SS3 34.456	0.000
					Residual	127.068	364	349							
					Total	803.650	370								
DV:AE2 IDV:SS1-10	0.913	0.834	0.832	0.6268	Regression	720.515	6	120.086	305.649	0.000	SS4 0.938	SS 4.026	SS 4.058	SS4 36.889	0.000
					Residual	141.011	364	0.393							
					Total	863.526	370								

*AE1: I spend most of the time on FB. AE2: FB is a motivational factor to complete the academic endeavors AE3: FB helps me in new concepts. Increasing interaction with course convenor and fellow students. SP1: FB usage affects the mindset of students SP2: It affects the social interaction amongst the students SP7: It gives social identity TP5: I trust the information shared by others on the FB. TP9: Interpersonal trust level is high in FB. SS3: It is a necessity for socioeconomically sound students to be on FB. SS4: The Status of the person is derived out of his friends list on FB